

Acute respiratory tract infections in SARS-CoV-2-negative children during the COVID-19 pandemic

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Summary

During the early stage of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, detection of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) was a priority; however, influenza viruses and RSV continued to cause seasonal epidemics complicating the diagnostic strategies. In the present study we estimated the proportion of SARS-CoV-2-negative pediatric

cases attributed to respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) and influenza viruses during a 3-month period after the identification of the first COVID-19 case in Greece. Ninety SARS-CoV-2-negative children hospitalized with acute respiratory tract infection were included in the study. Following a SARS-CoV-2 negative result, the samples were tested by molecular methods for detection of RSV and influenza viruses. The positive samples were further tested for identification of the subtype of the viruses.

We detected RSV or influenza viruses in 22 (24.4%) samples. Influenza virus was detected in 13 (14.4%) patients (two of type A and 11 of type B), and RSV (all RSV-A) was detected in 9 (10%) patients.

In conclusion, a syndromic approach for simultaneous detection of at least influenza virus, SARS-CoV-2 and RSV will be beneficial for the prompt implementation of appropriate hospital management including antiviral treatment and isolation measures.

Key words

respiratory infection; influenza; RSV; children

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Introduction

Current data show that severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) infections during childhood are usually asymptomatic or mild, and only few patients require hospitalization.^{1,2} Even within family clusters, it has been shown that children are more likely to have asymptomatic SARS-CoV-2 infection and present lower viral load as compared to adults.³ Therefore, the prevalence of coronavirus disease-2019 (COVID-19) is significantly lower in children than in adults.⁴ In Greece, the confirmed SARS-CoV-2 infections in the age group of 0-17 years have accounted for the 6.4% of the total number of cases reported to the National Public Health Organization (NPHO),⁵ prior to the emergence of more transmissible variants of concern, particularly Delta and Omicron.

The first COVID-19 case in Greece was diagnosed on 26th of February 2020 in Thessaloniki, Northern Greece. The early weeks of the pandemic coincided with the circulation of seasonal influenza viruses and respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), which cause respiratory symptoms similar to those of COVID-19 in children. All three viruses are characterized by direct person-to-person transmission; however, special isolation and quarantine measures have to be taken for COVID-19 cases. Due to the increased fear for COVID-19 and the need for preventive measures, respiratory samples were sent to our laboratory, one of the first SARS-CoV-2 reference laboratories in Greece.

The aim of the present study was to estimate the proportion of SARS-CoV-2-negative pediatric cases attributed to RSV and influenza viruses during a 3-month period after the identification of the first COVID-19 case in Greece.

Methods

Patients and samples

Ninety SARS-CoV-2-negative children hospitalized with acute respiratory tract infection during the three months-period after the first detection of COVID-19 case in Greece (February 26 to May 25, 2020) were included in the study. The median age of the patients was 3.4 years (range 0-14 years) and 51 (56.7%) were males. Nasopharyngeal swab samples in viral transport medium were sent to the laboratory for molecular detection of the virus.

Molecular methods

RNA was extracted from nasopharyngeal swab samples using the Qiagen Viral RNA mini kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The initial testing was performed using a commercial kit for SARS-CoV-2 detection (Viasure, Cer-Test Biotec, Zaragoza, Spain). Following a SARS-CoV-2 negative result, the samples were tested for the two types of influenza virus type A and B, while the subtyping of influenza A virus (H3 or H1pdmo09) and the influenza B virus lineage-genotyping were performed using the CDC real-time one step RT-PCR kit for influenza provided by the International Reagent Resource (<https://www.internationalreagentresource.org/>). Samples were also tested for RSV by applying a previ-

ously described PCR protocol capable to distinguish between the two RSV types, A and B.⁶

Results

RSV or influenza viruses were detected in 22 (24.4%) children (Table 1). Specifically, influenza virus was detected in 13 (14.4%) patients (two of type A and 11 of type B), and RSV (all RSV-A) in 9 (10%) patients. The median ages of children with influenza and RSV infection were 9.8 and 0.7 years, respectively.

One influenza A virus was subtyped as AH3N2, while subtyping was not possible in the second influenza virus A strain due to low viral load. Nine influenza B viruses belonged to B/Victoria lineage and two were not genotyped due to low viral load. Type A influenza viruses were detected only in February, while type B viruses were detected only in March and April.

The clinical symptoms ranged from mild (fever, malaise, rhinorrhoea and cough) to bronchiolitis (in RSV cases) and severe pneumonia. The patients were hospitalized for 3-5 days, except one 3-week old neonate with RSV bronchiolitis who was hospitalized for 9 days.

RSV and influenza co-circulated in March and April 2020, while RSV continued to be detected also in May, when influenza season was already over. Co-infection with RSV and influenza virus was not detected.

Table 1 Monthly detection of respiratory syncytial virus and influenza viruses in COVID-19 negative symptomatic children, northern Greece, February-May 2020. Co-infections were not detected.

Month	No of cases	Influenza		RSV*	Total No of RSV or Influenza v. cases
		No (%)	Type	No (%)	No (%)
26-29 February	8	3 (37.5)	1 AH3N2, 1 A untypable; 1B unsubtyped	0 (0)	3 (37.5)
1-31 March	27	7 (25.9)	7 B/Victoria-lineage	5 (18.5)	12 (44.4)
1-30 April	36	3 (8.3)	2 B/Victoria-lineage, 1B unsubtyped	2 (5.5)	5 (13.9)
1-25 May	19	0 (0)		2 (10.5)	2 (10.5)
Total	90	13 (14.4)	1 AH3N2, 1 A untypable; 9 B/Victoria-lineage, 2B untypable	9 (10.0)	22 (24.4)

*All RSV-A

Discussion

During the early stage of COVID-19 pandemic, detection of SARS-CoV-2 was a priority. The emergence of SARS-CoV-2 in Greece (26 February 2020) occurred when influenza activity had passed its peak (the peak was at week 6 of 2020). The influenza season in Greece usually starts in late December and lasts until early April, peaking in January or early February. The seasonal surveillance programme of NPHO on cases of influenza-like illness is active from week 40 of previous year to week 20 of the next year.^{7,8} Similarly, RSV activity peaks usually in February, but it may last longer during spring.

In the present study we tested samples from SARS-CoV-2-negative pediatric patients who were hospitalized with acute respiratory tract infection during a 3-month period after the first report of COVID-19 in Greece. We found that 24.4% of cases were caused by influenza viruses (14.4%) and RSV (10%). A recent contact with a clinically suspected COVID-19 case was noted in the patient referral of four influenza-positive cases that, most probably, were also influenza cases.

During the 2019-2020 influenza season, both A(H1N1)pdm09 and A(H3N2) were circulating in Greece, with the majority belonging to the A(H3N2) subtype; influenza B viruses, mainly of the B/Victoria lineage, started to circulate later, outnumbering the influenza A viruses (<https://eody.gov.gr/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/20.2020-FLU-WEEK-1.pdf>). Similarly, in other European countries, influenza A(H1N1)pdm09, A(H3N2) and B/Victoria circulated during 2019/20 season, with more type A than type B viruses detected in hospitalised patients, while for type B viruses, B/Victoria lineage viruses predominated (<https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/seasonal-influenza>). Typically, influenza B virus circulates during the end of influenza season, and this was the case in Greece during 2019/20 (<https://eody.gov.gr/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/20.2020-FLU-WEEK-1.pdf>). Accordingly in the present study, influenza A virus was detected only in February, while all influenza cases in March and April were caused by influenza B virus.

Influenza B is detected especially among children and young teenagers,⁹⁻¹¹ while RSV is the leading cause of acute bronchiolitis in infants and young children. In our study, the patients with influenza were older than those with RSV infection (median age 9.8 versus 0.7 years). In a study conducted in Greece in children under the age of 2 years, who were hospitalized during 2016-2018 for bronchiolitis, RSV was detected in 52.1%, and most patients were younger than 6 months.¹² In that study, RSV-A predominated during the 2016/17 season, while RSV-B predominated during 2017/18. It was shown that RSV-A and RSV-B sequences clustered within the ON1 and BA genotypes, respectively.¹² In the present study all RSV strains belonged to RSV-A (genotyping was not performed).

It is expected that the public health measures implemented by the countries to reduce SARS-CoV-2 transmission will reduce the transmission of other respiratory viruses.¹³ However, influenza A and B viruses and RSV will continue to cause winter-seasonal epidemics of respiratory illness, and their expected co-circulation with SARS-CoV-2 in the forthcoming seasons will complicate the diagnostic strategies, while co-infections cannot be excluded. Therefore, a syndromic approach is needed, and for this reason, SARS-CoV-2 has unavoidably been added to the panel of in-house and commercial multiplex assays, in order to detect a variety of respiratory pathogens or combination of at least influenza virus, SARS-CoV-2 and RSV. By this way appropriate hospital management including antiviral treatment and isolation measures would be implemented promptly.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Περίληψη

Οξείες λοιμώξεις του αναπνευστικού σε παιδιά αρνητικά για SARS-CoV-2 κατά την COVID-19 πανδημία

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Κατά τα πρώτα στάδια της πανδημίας της νόσου του κορονοϊού 2019 (coronavirus disease 2019, COVID-19), παρόλο που η ανίχνευση του κορονοϊού σοβαρού οξέος αναπνευστικού συνδρόμου 2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2, SARS-CoV-2) αποτελούσε προτεραιότητα, ο ιός της γρίπης και ο αναπνευστικός συγκυτιακός ιός (RSV) εξακολουθούσαν να προκαλούν εποχικά επιδημικά κύματα, με αποτέλεσμα να περιπλέκουν τη διαγνωστική στρατηγική. Στην παρούσα μελέτη, εκτιμήθηκε το ποσοστό των αρνητικών για τον SARS-CoV-2 παιδιατρικών περιστατικών λοιμώξεων αναπνευστικού, που αποδόθηκαν στους ιούς γρίπης και RSV κατά τη διάρκεια του πρώτου τριμήνου μετά την ανίχνευση του πρώτου περιστατικού COVID-19 στην Ελλάδα. Στη μελέτη συμπεριλήφθηκαν 90 παιδιατρικοί ασθενείς με συμπτωματολογία οξείας λοίμωξης αναπνευστικού, που βρέθηκαν αρνητικοί για τον SARS-CoV-2. Μετά από τον έλεγχο των δειγμάτων, τα αρνητικά για παρουσία SARS-CoV-2 δείγματα ελέγχθηκαν περαιτέρω με μοριακό έλεγχο για την ανίχνευση του RSV και του ιού της γρίπης. Τα θετικά δείγματα υποβλήθηκαν σε υποτυποποίηση. Ο ιός της γρίπης και ο RSV ανιχνεύθηκαν σε 22 (24.4%) δείγματα. Ο ιός της γρίπης ανιχνεύθηκε σε 13 (14.4%) ασθενείς (2 τύπου Α και 11 τύπου Β), και ο ιός RSV (όλοι RSV-A) ανιχνεύθηκε σε 9 (10%) ασθενείς. Συμπερασματικά, η συνδρομική προσέγγιση, με ταυτόχρονη ανίχνευση τουλάχιστον των ιών της γρίπης, του SARS-CoV-2 και του ιού RSV, θα ήταν χρήσιμη για την άμεση εφαρμογή μέτρων διαχείρισης στο νοσοκομείο, συμπεριλαμβανομένων της αντιϊκής θεραπείας και μέτρων απομόνωσης.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

λοιμώξεις αναπνευστικού, γρίπη, RSV, παιδιά

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